

Tuning the Size, Shape and the Magnetic Properties of Iron Oxide Nanoparticles

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Abstract: The influence of a variety of parameters on the synthesis of iron oxide nanoparticles (magnetite/maghemite $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4/\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$) by thermal decomposition of a metal-organic iron precursor in an organic medium is reported. We study the role of both the surfactant and reducing agent on the shape, size distribution and the magnetic properties. We aim at synthesizing magnetic nanoparticles with high crystal quality and good magnetic response. A narrow size distribution of pseudo-spherical and faceted particles (4 – 20 nm) with a high saturation magnetization ($M_s \approx 80\text{-}85$ emu/g at 5 K) is obtained when using oleic acid as a surfactant. In contrast, decanoic acid yields much larger pseudo-cubic particles (45 nm) with a wider size distribution and a larger saturation magnetization ($M_s = 92$ emu/g at 5 K), close to the expected value for bulk magnetite. Besides, the use of a variety of reducing agents monitors the magnetic behavior. In the case of 1,2-hexadecanediol, magnetic characterization suggests that the nanoparticles have uniform oxidation. However, those particles prepared without the use of any

reducing agent also show uniform oxidation just with a slightly smaller value of the saturation magnetization ($M_s = 76$ emu/g at 5 K). In contrast, hydrazine seems to promote a non-uniform oxidation that results in the appearance of the exchange bias phenomenon and in a smaller saturation magnetization ($M_s = 67$ emu/g at 5 K). New ways to tune the shape, size as well as the magnetic properties are discussed.

Introduction

The questions about the influence of different aspects on the synthesis of nanoparticles (NP), such as ambient atmosphere and use of reducing agents or surfactants, are relevant to understand the properties of the obtained materials. Magnetic NP are an ideal system to study finite-size and surface effects, all these yielding new interesting phenomena and enhanced properties with respect to their bulk counterpart.¹ Besides, surface chemistry is of great importance to determine the chemical and physical properties of NP² and, in particular, it tunes the size and shape of the NP. As the size decreases, surface effects become more significant due to the increasing fraction of surface atoms, while the crystal symmetry is reduced for those metallic cations lying at the particle surface due to incomplete atomic coordination. The magnetic structure at the surface layer is different from that in the core of the NP which has a strong effect on the magnetic properties.³⁻⁵ Consequently, understanding the influence of surface chemistry on the magnetic properties of NP certainly facilitates our fundamental view of their unique magnetic behavior, such as for example the actual origin of the magnetic hysteresis in single domain magnetic NP.

Moreover, understanding and controlling the effects of surface chemistry on the magnetic properties have become increasingly important for the technological applications of magnetic NP, such as high-density magnetic storage media, magnetic resonance imaging or drug delivery.⁶⁻¹⁰ The use of magnetic NP for biomedical applications is likely to bring about significant advances in the diagnosis, prevention,

and the treatment of diseases. The potential application of magnetic NP for biomedical purposes relies on the synthesis of high quality materials from both the crystalline and magnetic points of view. In this sense, it is essential for their use to minimize the poly-dispersion and heterogeneity, and to maximize their magnetic response. For example, magnetic NP for magnetically-guided site-specific drug delivery or magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) contrast-enhancement agents must present a good magnetic behavior and a modified biocompatible surface with ligands and/or polymer matrices that also serve as drug carrying vehicles. It has been proposed that superparamagnetic NP at room temperature are best suited to accomplish those goals since NP agglomeration is avoided.

Synthesis based on metal-organic precursors has proved successful for the preparation of uniform NP.¹¹⁻¹⁶ This method is used due to the ease and reproducibility to synthesize uniform and highly crystalline particles and, recently, Hyeon and coworkers have improved the synthesis procedure in order to increase the size range.¹⁷ The as synthesized iron oxide NP (magnetite/maghemite $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4/\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$) by thermal decomposition of an organic iron precursor in an organic medium allows the preparation of highly crystalline NP with excellent magnetic properties.³⁻⁴ However, a variety of aspects (atmosphere, reducing agent, surfactant, precursor, solvent and other parameters) make the synthesis critical. Monitoring the effect of those factors on the magnetic behavior, as well as on the size and shape distributions, is of great relevance for developing NP suitable for biomedical applications.

This report attempts to address, from both chemical and physical point of views, the influence of the reducing agent and surfactant on the synthesis of iron oxide NP. However, absolute control over the shape and size distribution remains a challenge, and the formation mechanisms leading to iron oxides under different conditions are under current discussion, yet.

Experimental Section

High quality iron oxide NP may be prepared by thermal decomposition at high temperature of an organic iron precursor in an organic medium. The most usual procedure starts from iron (III)

acetylacetonate as iron source, 1,2-hexadecanediol as reducing agent to obtain both iron atomic species Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} and oleic acid as surfactant to promote steric hindering and avoid NP agglomeration.^{12,15} In this work, some modifications of this receipt are discussed. Decanoic acid is used as new capping ligand while hydrazine is used as reducing agent. Iron (III) acetylacetonate (99%), dibenzylether (99%) and decanoic (96%) acid were purchased by Acros Organics. Hydrazine (anhydrous) (98%), oleic acid (90%) 1,2-hexadecanediol (90%) and oleylamine (70%) were purchased by Sigma-Aldrich. All reactants were used in the synthesis without further purification. Taking into account the large number of non-independent variables that affect the final output, three different samples were prepared as follows:

Synthesis S1: Particles were synthesized from a mixture of 0.71 g of iron (III) acetylacetonate (2 mmol), 1.69 g of oleic acid (8 mmol) and 50 ml of dibenzylether. The solution was heated to 200 °C for 2 hours, stirred under a flow of argon gas and then heated to reflux for 60 min in the same flow of argon gas. The solution was washed several times with acetone and ethanol, and stored in hexane and oleic acid. To precipitate the powder, a small volume of the colloid was washed in isopropanol, centrifuged and dried at room temperature under an argon flow. This sample was labeled as S1. Note that no reducing agent was used in this synthesis.

Synthesis S2: Particles were synthesized from a mixture of 0.71 g of iron (III) acetylacetonate (2 mmol), 1.69 g of oleic acid (8 mmol), 50 ml of dibenzylether and 1 ml of hydrazine. The solution was heated to 200 °C for 2 hours with vigorous stirring under an argon flow and then heated to reflux for 60 min in the same flow of argon gas. The same procedure than in sample S1 was used to wash, storage and precipitate the NP. This sample was labeled as S2.

Synthesis S3: In this synthesis oleic acid was replaced by decanoic acid. A mixture of 0.71 g of iron (III) acetylacetonate (2 mmol), 1.42 g of decanoic acid (8 mmol) and 50 ml of dibenzylether was heated to 200 °C for 2 hours under stirring and a flow of argon gas. Then, the solution was heated to reflux temperature for 60 min in the same flow of argon gas. The solution was washed several times with

acetone and ethanol. The NP were precipitated and dried at room temperature under an argon flow. This sample was labeled as S3.

Two more samples were prepared in order to compare samples S1, S2 and S3 to those obtained by other synthesis methods in literature. In this latter case, we followed the standard procedure reported in Ref. ¹⁵. Iron oxide NP of about 4 nm and coated with oleic acid were synthesized from a mixture of 0.71 g of iron (III) acetylacetonate (2 mmol), 2.38 g of 1,2-hexadecanediol (10 mmol), 1.69 g of oleic acid (6 mmol), 1.60 g of oleylamine (6 mmol) and 20 ml of phenyl ether. The solution was heated up to 200 °C for two hours under vigorous stirring and an argon gas flow. The mixture was then heated to reflux for 1 hour and washed following the same procedure as described above for the samples S1, S2 and S3. This sample was labeled as 4 nm-oleic (standard). Finally, a sample with a mean particle size of about 17 nm was prepared using 0.71 g of iron (III) acetylacetonate (2 mmol), 2.38 g of 1,2-hexadecanediol (10 mmol), 1.69 g of oleic acid (6 mmol), 1.60 g of oleylamine (6 mmol) and 20 ml of octyl ether. The solution was heated up to 200 °C for two hours under vigorous stirring and an argon gas flow. The mixture was then heated to reflux for 1 hour and washed following the same procedure as described above for the samples S1, S2 and S3. This sample was labeled as 17 nm-oleic (standard).

Structural, microstructural and magnetic characterization

Particle size and shape were studied by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) using 200 KeV JEOL-2000 FXII and 120 KeV MT80-Hitachi microscopes. TEM samples were prepared by placing one drop of a dilute particle suspension in tetrahydrofuran on a carbon-coated copper grid and evaporating the solvent at room temperature. The mean particle size (D_{TEM}) and size distribution were evaluated by measuring at least 100 particles (Table I). Figure 1 shows TEM images of samples S1, S2 and S3. Figure 2 shows TEM images of samples 4 nm-oleic (standard) and 17 nm-oleic (standard).

Figure 1. TEM images of the iron oxide NP: (a) sample S1, (b) sample S2, and (c) sample S3.

Figure 2. TEM images of the iron oxide NP: (left-hand side) 4 nm particles, and (right-hand side) 17 nm particles, synthesized by a standard procedure.

The crystal structure of the samples was identified by X-ray power diffraction performed in a Phillips 1710 diffractometer using Cu K α radiation. The patterns were collected within 5° and 80° in 2 θ . The XRD spectra were indexed to an inverse spinel structure. The mean particle diameters obtained from

XRD (D_{XRD}) are given in Table I.

Magnetic characterization was carried out in a Quantum Design SQUID magnetometer. Hysteresis loops $M(H)$ were measured under a maximum applied field of ± 50 kOe at 5 K (Figure 4), in order to evaluate the coercive field, H_C , and saturation magnetization, M_S . Saturation magnetization was obtained by extrapolating to zero field the experimental $M(H)$ curve from the high-field range where the magnetization varies linearly with H , namely, $M(H) \approx M_S + \chi_d H$, χ_d being the high-field differential susceptibility that accounts for the surface spin disorder.¹⁸⁻¹⁹ Hysteresis loops were normalized to the total iron-oxide mass, taking into account the percentage of surfactant. Thermogravimetric analyses (TGA) were performed to evaluate the percentage of organic matter, using a Mettler TGA/SDTA851. Samples were heated from room temperature up to 700 °C with a heating rate of 10 °C/min under a nitrogen atmosphere. Zero-field-cooling (ZFC) and field cooling (FC) magnetization curves were measured at 50 Oe in the temperature range 5 K – 300 K. (Figure 5).

Figure 3. X-Ray diffraction patterns of samples S1, S2 and S3, together with the indexation of the Bragg peaks to an inverse spinel structure.

Figure 4. Hysteresis loops of the iron oxide nanoparticles synthesized with different methods. Inset: detail of the low field region to evaluate the coercive fields.

Figure 5. ZFC-FC curves for all samples measured at 50 Oe.

In a distribution of magnetic NP, the ZFC/FC magnetization curves yield information on both the distribution of blocking temperatures and dipolar inter-particle interactions. These curves are measured

as follows. The sample is cooled from high temperature (300 K in our case) down to 5 K, without the application of any magnetic field, so that the magnetic NPs are progressively blocked randomly. Once at the lowest temperature, a very small magnetic field is set (e.g. 50 Oe) and magnetization is then measured as temperature is increased so as to obtain the ZFC curve. Once back at high temperature, the sample is cooled down again while a small magnetic field is applied. Magnetic NPs are progressively blocked along the magnetic field axis and the FC magnetization is measured.

Typically, the ZFC curve first increases with temperature as the magnetic field partially aligns the magnetization of the NP, reaching a maximum at a temperature T_M , thus indicating that the magnetic moment of each particle is blocked along its easy magnetization direction at a temperature T , which depends on the particle volume, anisotropy and orientation. As the samples are constituted of a random assembly of crystallites that presents a certain volume distribution, $f(V)$, each crystallite is blocked at a different temperature T_B . As a result, we observe a distribution of blocking temperatures $F(T_B)$ yielding a broad peak in the ZFC curve. T_M is related to the mean blocking temperature $\langle T_B \rangle$ as $T_M \approx 2 \langle T_B \rangle$, when the particle size distribution is log-normal and in the absence of relevant dipolar interactions. Besides, the ZFC magnetization strongly decreases below the peak at T_M , as the NP become superparamagnetic. In contrast, the FC curve monotonically increases as $1/T$ (Curie law) in an assembly of non-interacting particles, while strong dipolar inter-particle interactions yield a flat FC curve at temperatures below T_M . Finally, the existence of a wide particle size distribution, particle agglomeration and/or inter-particle interactions is also suggested by the fact that the irreversibility between the ZFC and FC curves starts at a temperatures above T_M . A detailed account for all the foregoing may be found in Ref. ¹⁸. Table I summarizes the structural, microstructural and magnetic parameters of all 5 samples.

	S1	S2	S3	4 nm	17 nm
D_{TEM} (nm)	7.4(0.8)	8.1(0.7)	45(9)	4.2(0.5)	17(1)
D_{XRD} (nm)	7.2(0.7)	8.2(0.5)	46(5)	3.9(0.5)	16.8(0.8)
T_{M} (K)	28(1)	49(1)	>275	19(2)	>275
M_{S} (emu/g)	70(2)	65(1)	92(3)	75(1)	82(1)
H_{C} (Oe)	270(2)	70 (10)	340 (12)	318(6)	364(8)

Table I. Mean particle size obtained from TEM (D_{TEM}) and XRD (D_{XRD}), temperature of the maximum of the ZFC curve (T_{M}), saturation magnetization (M_{S}), and coercive field (H_{C}) for samples S1, S2, S3, 4 nm-oleic (standard) and 17 nm-oleic (standard). The values in parenthesis indicate the experimental error of the data.

Results and Discussion

The detailed knowledge of the chemical reactions and kinetics in the non-hydrolytic synthesis of magnetic NP is of great interest and would allow controlling their physical and chemical properties. Most papers in literature use 1,2-hexadecanediol to synthesize iron oxide NP and reduce maghemite ($\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$) to magnetite (Fe_3O_4).²⁰ Also, amines are typically used as co-surfactant^{11,15,21}, all the foregoing leading to iron oxide NP with a narrow size and shape distributions, and high magnetic quality. In particular, it has been recently reported that slightly modification of this procedure allows obtaining single crystal magnetite Fe_3O_4 NP with a good control of the particle size in the range 4-20 nm and with an almost size-independent saturation magnetization of within 78-92 emu/g at low temperature^{3-4,20} which is close to the bulk value (98 emu/g).²² As far as we know, those values are among the largest values of M_{S} for iron oxide NP that may be found in literature, which are typically much lower due to surface spin disorder (see for example $M_{\text{S}} \approx 56$ emu/g for 5 nm NP in Ref. ²³ and $M_{\text{S}} \approx 47$ emu/g for 5 nm NP in Ref. ²⁴). We note that bulk maghemite shows $M_{\text{S}} \approx 83.5$ emu/g²² - 87.4 emu/g²⁵ at low temperature. High quality $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ NPs with size in the range 5-12 nm and reduced surface spin disorder

show size-independent $M_s \approx 76-77$ emu/g at low temperature.²⁰ In order to compare all those results in literature to samples S1, S2 and S3, samples 4 nm-oleic (standard) and 17 nm-oleic (standard) were prepared and used as reference samples. All particles were single crystals, as expected from the synthesis method.⁵

The role of the reducing agent: The first step of the work was to prove how 1,2-hexadecanediol affects the synthesis and magnetic properties. When no reducing agent was used (sample S1), pseudo-spherical and faceted iron oxide NPs of about 7.5 nm with a narrow size distribution are formed (Figure 1a), which are very similar to those of 4 nm-oleic (standard) (Figure 2). Consequently, the ZFC-FC curves (Figure 5) show similar trends as well: the ZFC curves evidence a narrow size distribution, with a rapid increase of the signal up to temperature of the maximum, $T_M \approx 28$ K and 19 K, respectively for sample S1 and 4 nm-oleic (standard) - the latter being slightly lower due to smaller mean particle size-, and Curie–Weiss-like $1/T$ behaviour above T_M . The values of T_M for both samples are in agreement with the effective magnetic anisotropy of high saturation magnetization iron oxide NP.^{3-4,26} The progressive increase of the FC curve below T_M indicates that dipolar interactions, although may not be negligible, have been largely reduced due to the surfactant taking the particles apart in the case of sample 4 nm-oleic (standard), while the flatter FC for sample S1 below T_M suggests that dipolar interactions are not so effectively reduced. We must note that the dipolar field created by a magnetic particle is roughly proportional to its magnetic moment (i.e., to the particle volume) and decreases as the third power of distance. As a result, the increase in the mean particle size in sample S1 has a strong effect of the mean magnetic moment per particle, while the average inter-particle distance remains almost the same (i.e., about twice the length of the oleic acid carbon chain). Finally, the fact that the ZFC and FC curves for sample S1 join at about T_M suggests that aggregates are almost not present, in agreement with the individual particle coating and the pseudo-self-assembly showing in Figure 1(a). Furthermore, $M_s \approx 70$ (2) emu/g for sample S1 (Figure 4), which is slightly smaller than that of the

standard sample ($M_s \approx 75$ (1) emu/g). One can conclude that the absence of 1,2-hexadecanediol seems not to affect too much on the iron oxide stoichiometry (Fe^{2+} versus Fe^{3+} ratio), the NP always being a mixture of magnetite and maghemite. This opens the unsolved question on the actual reducing agent when Fe(III) acetylacetonate is used as iron precursor to obtain Fe_3O_4 NP. The maghemite $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ phase may come in the form of an over-oxidized shell surrounding a magnetite-like Fe_3O_4 particle core. This arises from the fact that the magnetite and maghemite form a solid solution. For example, for a case of 5 nm particles similar to those in samples S1 and 4 nm-oleic (standard), Mössbauer spectroscopy gave an estimate of about a 21% of maghemite²⁰, while X-ray magnetic circular dichroism (XMCD) gave an estimate of about a maximum of 50% for exactly the same sample.⁵

The second step was to use a strong reducing agent, such as, for example, hydrazine (sample S2). In this case, when 1 ml of hydrazine was injected into the solution, a violent reaction was observed, leading to iron oxide NP with an average size about 8 nm and a slightly more irregular shape (Figure 3b) but still displaying a narrow size distribution of magnetic cores (see the ZFC-FC in Figure 5).²⁶ The ZFC/FC curves are consistent with the two samples discussed above. The ZFC evidences a narrow size distribution, with $T_M \approx 49$ K, such that T_M increases with increasing particle size and interactions, as the distance among particles is not enough to reduce the dipolar interactions. The FC curve is thus flat below T_M , as usually observed for iron oxide NP above about 8 nm in diameter. The ZFC and FC curves also join together at about T_M , suggesting that aggregates are almost no present, in agreement with the individual particle coating and the pseudo-self-assembly in Figure 1(b). However, $M_s \approx 65$ (1) emu/g, (Figure 4) is smaller than the corresponding values for samples S1 and 4 nm-oleic (standard).

In order to shed some light on the reduced value of M_s for sample S2, the hysteresis loop $M(H)$ at 5 K was measured after the sample was cooled from 300 K down to 5 K while a magnetic field of 2 kOe was applied. As shown in Figure 6, the hysteresis loop after this field cooling (FC) process is shifted towards negative magnetic field values (i.e., opposite to the direction of the cooling field).

Figure 6. Hysteresis loop of sample S2 after a field cooling process at 20 kOe.

This phenomenon is known as exchange bias and results from the magnetic exchange interactions between a ferromagnet (FM) and an antiferromagnetic (AFM) in intimate contact.²⁷ Exchange bias (EB) was first reported for core/shell FM/AFM Co/CoO NP²⁸⁻³⁰, and has been extensively studied in thin film AFM/FM bilayers^{27,31} since it fixes a spin reference state that it is used in all magnetic field sensors, such as for example, read heads in magnetic recording³²⁻³³ and magnetic tunnel junctions in new magnetic random access memories.³⁴ It is well established that the AFM sets a unidirectional anisotropy on the FM that the latter senses as a magnetic field that it is superimposed to the external applied field, resulting in a loop shift. Typically, the parameters used to characterize EB are the coercive field,

$$H_c = \frac{|H_c^1 - H_c^2|}{2},$$

and the loop shift (exchange field),

$$H_{EB} = \frac{|H_c^1 + H_c^2|}{2},$$

where $H_C^1 = -140 \pm 7$ Oe and $H_C^2 = 15 \pm 2$ Oe are the coercive fields for the decreasing and increasing branches of the hysteresis loop, respectively. With these results, $H_{EB} = 63 \pm 10$ Oe and $H_C = 78 \pm 10$ Oe.

We note that except for sample S2, all other samples in this paper do not show any EB phenomenon after a FC process. The existence of the EB effect is probably related to the non-uniform oxygen distribution throughout the particle. The slow chemical reactivity of 1,2-hexadecanediol may produce a slow reduction rate. The new ions that are incorporated to the surface build a new layer allowing a uniform oxygen concentration throughout the particle until the end of the synthesis. The same argument holds in the case that no reducing agent is used. In contrast, hydrazine is known to be a strong reducing agent. This highly reactive behaviour may promote a heterogeneous reduction. This heterogeneous reduction may generate a kind of layer-by-layer structure, where each layer has a different oxidation rate. The presence of layers with different oxygen content allows the formation of different iron oxides phases whose magnetic behaviour may be either AFM or ferrimagnetic depending on the oxygen stoichiometry, which could explain the appearance of EB, as observed in many NP systems.²⁹ It is also worth noticing that synthesis with a higher amount of hydrazine (about 2 and 3 ml; results not shown) led to a non uniform particle shape. This may occur due to either the presence of water formed from the Wolf-Kichner reaction where hydrazine oxides to N_2 , or to the complexation of hydrazine. The non uniform particle shape could also result from the different growing rates of the crystallographic planes.

Finally, all hysteresis loops in Figure 4 suggest that samples are high quality from the magnetic point of view, which makes them suitable for potential biomedical applications. First, all $M(H)$ curves saturate at relatively low fields. In order to give a criteria to compare to other samples in literature, we may define the saturation field, H_s , as the field for which the experimental magnetization is about 90% of its value at 50 kOe (maximum applied field). H_s is below 2 kOe for all samples. Second, above the saturation field, the magnetization curves are almost flat, i.e., $M(H) \approx M_s + \chi_d H$, χ_d being the high-field differential susceptibility that accounts for the surface spin disorder.¹⁸⁻¹⁹ Typical values for χ_d in samples

S1 and S2 are of the order of 10^{-5} emu/g, one order of magnitude smaller than other iron oxide NP in literature.²³ Third, the reasonable high M_s values give further support to the idea that high temperature synthesis associated to the thermal decomposition of an organic precursor in organic medium yields NP with high crystal and magnetic quality. As in the superparamagnetic regime at room temperature the key magnetic parameter is the magnetic susceptibility ($\chi = M/H$), search for high saturation magnetization is required, since $\chi \sim M_s^2$. This is relevant for biomedical applications where magnetic NP must show a large response under the application of small magnetic fields. These results suggest that the higher the crystallinity and the lower the spin disorder, the better.

The role of the surfactant: The influence of the capping ligand in the synthesis of magnetic NP is also a challenging issue. Common procedures in thermal decomposition use oleic acid as a surfactant because of its high boiling point. Oleic acid is an eighteen carbon chain with a double bond between the ninth and tenth carbon atoms. Other fatty acids, such as stearic, lauric or decanoic acids, present the same structure than oleic acid but without the double bond. It is relevant to notice that the double bond seems to make the chain more stable, avoiding it to fold up. Besides, the role of the amount of carbon atoms in the chain is neither clear. Some works where the synthesis starts from iron pentacarbonyl propose the catalytic behaviour of the carboxylic group on the decomposition of the latter.³⁵

In our case, we start from Fe (III) acetylacetonate, making the influence of the chain length of capping ligand different. In any case, the presence of a carboxyl group allows the formation of iron carboxylates (iron organic complexes) that may play a relevant role in the nucleation and growth of the NP.³⁶ The reasons to choose decanoic acid are its lower boiling point as compared to oleic acid and its solubility in dibenzyl ether. Sample S3 used the same amount of surfactant (4 mmol), the same amount of iron precursor (2 mmol) and the same synthesis time as in S1. No oleylamine was used in this synthesis.

Figure 1(c) shows a TEM image of sample S3. Particles are pseudo-cubes of about 45 nm with a wide particle size distribution. The ZFC-FC curves in Figure 5 are almost flat, revealing that T_M is well above room temperature and that there are strong interactions among particles, as expected taking into account

the mean size of the particles. The effect of dipolar interactions can also be observed in some TEM images (Figure 1(c)), where the cubes tend to be aligned forming stripe-like structures, which help closing magnetic flux lines and reduce magnetostatic energy. However, other images suggest that some particles agglomerate, which is also compatible with magnetostatics and yields flux closure. Finally, the ZFC shows a peak about $(105 \pm 5 \text{ K})$ that suggests the occurrence of the Verwey transformation,^{20,37} which takes place at about 119 K in bulk magnetite. In addition, the magnetization curve in Figure 5 yields $M_s \approx 92(3) \text{ emu/g}$, very close to that of the bulk counterpart (98 emu/g is the theoretical value extrapolated at 0 K).²² Although M_s is slightly larger, the coercive field of sample S3 compares very well with that for sample 17 nm-oleic (standard). Finally, the previous statements concerning the high magnetic quality of samples also hold for samples S3 and 17 nm-oleic (standard). In conclusion, sample S3 may be taken as a magnetite bulk reference sample, whose magnetic parameters are, as far as we know, among the best ever reported for iron oxide NP^{3-4,38}.

On the other hand, the use of decanoic acid allows a new range of sizes easily reached by playing with the synthesis conditions.³⁸ In the synthesis of sample S3, the iron complex results from a different fatty acid with a shorter chain and without double bond. As well known, the synthesis proceeds through two steps, nucleation and growth.³⁹ It is extremely important to know, as much as possible, the activation temperatures for these regions. For oleic acid, temperatures and times are reported in a large number of papers.¹⁵ However, taking into account the differences on the boiling temperature of oleic and decanoic acids, it is likely that the formation and decomposition temperatures of the iron complex could be different. With the size distribution of S3, one can conclude that the nucleation temperature must be around 20 or 30 degrees lower than in the case of oleic acid. New syntheses with different temperatures and temperature rates are under investigation.

Besides, when substituting the oleic acid surfactant by decanoic acid, the NP transform from pseudo-spheres in the range 3-20 nm⁴⁰ into much bigger pseudo-cubes. There is some discussion on the literature about the shape of iron oxide nanoparticles in the case of oleic acid coating⁴¹⁻⁴², where the

most extended idea is that the affinity of the iron complex to some crystallographic planes avoids the spherical growing of the particle. Though, taken into account the differences described above, there seems to exist a faster dynamics at the NP surfaces in the case of decanoic acid, that is, a different kinetics, such that the exchange of ligands and ions between the solution and surface is faster. Particles are regular cubes due to their size and crystallinity, as they are expressing the cubic cell of the inverse spinel structure. In any case, understanding the influence of capping ligands on the synthesis of NP remains a big challenge.⁴³⁻⁴⁶

Conclusions

In this work, a variety of modifications of the synthesis of iron oxide NP based on the thermal decomposition of an organic precursor, are reported. All samples show excellent magnetic properties, which makes them suitable for biomedical applications once the NP are stable in aqueous medium, as some of us have recently shown⁴⁷. Magnetic resonance imaging of liver and brain has been successfully proven using iron oxide NP of about a few nanometers in size, once the oleic acid coating is ligand exchanged to dimercaptosuccinic acid.⁴⁷ In particular, we have shown that the reducing agent controls the uniform oxidation of the NP, while the capping ligand monitors the particle shape and size. In the former case, the use of hydrazine leads to the appearance of exchange bias. In the latter case, decanoic acid leads to regular pseudo-cubes with a broad size distribution due to the differences on the intermediate iron complex as compared to oleic acid. The new iron complex (iron decanoate) may have a different nature to the iron oleate, such that the nucleation and growth mechanisms could be different and a new time-temperature diagram should be found. Our results also suggest that 1,2-hexadecanediol seems not to affect too much on the iron oxide stoichiometry since the magnetic properties are not strongly modified when it is not used in the synthesis. This opens the unsolved question on the actual reducing agent when Fe(III) acetylacetonate is used as organic iron precursor to obtain Fe₃O₄ NP. We also note these excellent magnetic properties are very unusual in literature. We thus suggest that the

typical reduction of the magnetization in oxide NP,^{1,48} together with the glassy and exchange bias behaviour attributed to a spin-glass like phase at the particle surface^{1,48}, may be just related to the poor crystalline quality, since none of the latter are present in the high quality NP in this paper. In fact, Monte Carlo simulations of a single oxide NP show that surface spin disorder is not enough to promote exchange bias⁴⁹ and that the coexistence different magnetic phases within the NP is required.²⁹ The future directions of this work are to study new capping ligands, as well as to determine the appropriate time-temperature diagrams. The actual origin of both the exchange bias phenomena and high saturation magnetization of coated NP are under current study.

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